

Amperometric Determination of Lead with Diphenylthiovioluric Acid

N. R. Banerjee and R. P. Singh

Several methods for amperometric determination of lead have been described in literature¹⁻³. One of the authors³ had earlier reported that lead was precipitated from its salt solutions by the ammonium salt of diphenylthiovioluric acid. The present work was therefore carried out to explore the possibility of estimating small amounts of lead by the amperometric method.

Preliminary work shows that the precipitation of lead is almost complete in the pH range 6.0 to 6.9. To bring the pH within this range, the lead salt solutions were made 2% with respect to ammonium acetate. The latter also served as the supporting electrolyte. The solutions contained 0.02% of gelatin as a maximum suppressor. The metal concentration in the solutions used for titrations was approximately 0.001 *M* and that of the ammonium salt of diphenylthiovioluric acid was 0.01 *M*. A manual polarograph, manufactured by Adept Laboratories, Poona (India), was used for carrying out these investigations.

The polarograms of the ammonium salt of diphenylthiovioluric acid under the above conditions (pH 6.5) showed one well-defined wave with $E_4 = -0.495$ volts vs. S.C.E. The height of the wave was found to be proportional to the concentration of the reagent. From the diffusion current regions of the polarograms of lead and the ammonium salt of diphenylthiovioluric acid, the D.M.E. potential for amperometric estimation of lead was chosen as -0.7 volts vs. S.C.E. The titrations were carried out in an H-shaped cell.

Procedure.—A solution of lead nitrate (20 ml) was transferred to the cell and deaerated by passage of nitrogen. The solution was then titrated with the solution of ammonium salt of diphenylthiovioluric acid, added through a micro-burette graduated to read 0.02 ml. The reaction mixture was stirred after each addition of the titrant by bubbling nitrogen and the precipitate was allowed to settle clear of the capillary tip before diffusion current was measured. As the titration proceeded, the observed diffusion current decreased due to precipitation of lead. After the equivalence point, a rise was observed due to reduction of the ammonium salt of diphenylthiovioluric acid. The observed diffusion current after each addition of the reagent was corrected for the dilution effect. The plot of diffusion current versus the volume of the titrant added gave a V-shaped graph. The

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2. Khosla and Gaur, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, **13B**, 304.

3. Gambhir and Singh, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, **23A**, 330.

volume of the titrant at the equivalence point was determined from the intersections of the two linear portions of the graph. The composition of the precipitate at the equivalence point corresponds to PbD_2 (D =diphenylthioviolate ion). The results of a few such estimations are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

$Pb(NO_3)_2$ soln. taken = 20 ml. pH adjusted to 6.6. Reagent soln. = 0.01 *M*.
 $E_{de} = -0.7$ volts vs. S.C.E.

Sl. No.	Pb in soln.	Titre values.		%Error.
		Calc.	Obs.	
1	4.140 mg.	4.00 ml	4.12 ml	3.0
2	5.175	5.00	5.14	2.8
3	3.105	3.00	3.07	2.3
4	3.622	3.50	3.46	1.1
5	4.657	4.50	4.59	2.0

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
 UNIVERSITY OF DELHI,
 DELHI-6.

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